

Telepharmacy as an innovative concept for the delivery of pharmaceutical services in Bulgaria

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Received 22 March 2026 ♦ Accepted 8 April 2026 ♦ Published 23 April 2026

Citation: Grigorov E, Pesheva M (2026) Telepharmacy as an innovative concept for the delivery of pharmaceutical services in Bulgaria. *Pharmacia* 73: e192571. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e192571>

Abstract

Background and Aim: Telepharmacy has emerged as a transformative model for delivering pharmaceutical services remotely through digital and telecommunication technologies. In Bulgaria, persistent regional disparities in pharmacy distribution, a growing elderly population, and advancing digital infrastructure create both the need and the conditions for telepharmacy implementation. This narrative review aims to analyze the conceptual framework, technological prerequisites, regulatory landscape, and practical opportunities for telepharmacy within the Bulgarian healthcare system.

Methods: A structured literature search was conducted between December 2025 and March 2026 across PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar, supplemented by national regulatory documents and reports from international organizations. A total of 362 records were identified, of which 67 met the inclusion criteria. A thematic synthesis approach was applied to organize findings into major categories: conceptual frameworks, technological infrastructure, regulatory aspects, and practical applications.

Results: Telepharmacy encompasses four core components—remote pharmacist-patient communication, electronic prescribing and digital health records, therapy monitoring systems, and digital health promotion—applicable across community, hospital, and consultative domains. Bulgaria demonstrates favorable prerequisites for implementation, including 83% digital connectivity and an operational National Health Information System since 2020. However, significant barriers persist: telepharmacy lacks an explicit definition in national legislation, remote dispensing of prescription medicines is prohibited, and regional disparities in pharmacy coverage remain pronounced.

Conclusion: Telepharmacy represents a viable and promising strategy for improving equitable access to pharmaceutical care in Bulgaria, particularly in rural and underserved areas. Its full integration into the healthcare system requires the development of a clear regulatory framework, sustained investment in digital infrastructure, and coordinated collaboration among public authorities, academic institutions, and the pharmaceutical profession.

Keywords

digital pharmacist, patient-centered pharmacy, pharmaceutical activities, telepharmacy

Introduction

Pharmaceutical activities play a key role in modern healthcare systems by ensuring the safe, effective, and rational use of medicinal products. They are legally regulated by legislation

in every country. In the context of rapid digital transformation and the growing needs of the population, healthcare systems are undergoing significant changes aimed at improving both access to and quality of care (Poudel and Nissen 2016a; WHO 2021; Marinkovic et al. 2022; Quamed 2024).

One of the innovative concepts in this field is telepharmacy. The term telepharmacy emerged in the 1990s, shortly after the introduction of telemedicine, and has since become widely accepted (Angaran 1999). In subsequent years, it has been defined as “the provision of pharmacist care by registered pharmacists and pharmacies through the use of telecommunications to patients located at a distance” (Baldoni et al. 2019; Kilova 2020). To date, this core definition has remained largely unchanged. In summary, telepharmacy can be described as a conceptual model for the delivery of pharmaceutical services at a distance through the use of information and communication technologies (Clifton et al. 2003). This model enables remote consultations, public health promotion, medication therapy management, and, under specific regulatory conditions, the dispensing of medicinal products (RHHub n.d.).

In Bulgaria, where significant regional disparities in access to healthcare services persist—particularly in rural and remote areas—telepharmacy has the potential to become a rational and effective solution. According to data from the Digital Economy and Society Index, Bulgaria has improved its level of connectivity, reaching 83% in 2025, particularly regarding broadband coverage and internet access availability (including 5G) (DESI 2025). This technological framework is essential for the development of remote healthcare services (Ministry of Health 2025).

The availability of stable internet infrastructure is a key factor for the implementation of telepharmacy, especially in rural and sparsely populated areas. These regions often face limited access to pharmaceutical services due to the lack of pharmacies or healthcare professionals, making them the primary target group for telepharmacy solutions (Poudel and Nissen 2016a).

With the widespread availability of internet access, an increasing number of patients seek answers to everyday health-related questions online (Clarke et al. 2016). However, the information obtained is often inaccurate, incomplete, or not evidence-based, which may pose risks to patient safety (Clarke et al. 2016; Krumov et al. 2017; Pesheva and Ivanova 2023).

Innovation in telepharmacy is manifested as a fundamentally new approach to the delivery of pharmaceutical services through the integration of digital and telecommunication technologies into routine pharmacy practice. It does not merely represent a technological supplement but rather a substantial transformation of the pharmaceutical care model, in which interaction between the pharmacist and the patient is conducted remotely, independent of geographical and physical constraints (Clifton et al. 2003).

This approach introduces novel opportunities for real-time therapy monitoring, personalization of care, and more efficient utilization of professional resources (Marinkovic et al. 2022; Petrova et al. 2023; FIP n.d.). By overcoming traditional barriers related to access, time, and location of service provision, telepharmacy can be firmly regarded as a significant innovation that modernizes and

advances contemporary pharmacy practice (Kehrer et al. 2013; Clarke et al. 2016; Livet et al. 2021; Lizano-Díez et al. 2022; De Tran et al. 2023).

The present narrative review aims to analyze the nature, applications, advantages, and limitations of telepharmacy, as well as the opportunities for its implementation within the Bulgarian healthcare system.

Methodology

The structured literature search was conducted between December 2025 and March 2026. A total of 362 records were identified, of which 67 were included in the final analysis.

The study was conducted as a narrative review, based on a qualitative analysis of the existing scientific literature, regulatory documents, and reports from major international organizations. The aim of the review was to synthesize and critically summarize current knowledge and practices related to the development and implementation of telepharmacy. Unlike systematic reviews, narrative reviews allow for a broader and more interpretative synthesis of the literature, providing a comprehensive overview of the topic and highlighting key trends, concepts, and gaps in the existing evidence.

Literature search strategy

A literature search was conducted in the following electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. In addition to peer-reviewed scientific literature, relevant normative documents, policy papers, and reports from international organizations were also included to provide a broader contextual perspective.

The search was performed using a combination of controlled and free-text keywords. The main search terms included “telepharmacy,” “pharmaceutical care,” “digital health,” “remote pharmacy services,” and “Bulgaria.” Boolean operators (AND, OR) were applied where appropriate to refine the search strategy and ensure the retrieval of relevant studies.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: published primarily in English or Bulgarian; published from 2010 onwards to ensure relevance and alignment with recent developments in digital health; directly related to telepharmacy, pharmaceutical care, or digital health services; included peer-reviewed journal articles, official guidelines, policy documents, and reports from recognized international organizations.

Exclusion criteria were publications not relevant to the topic of telepharmacy or digital pharmaceutical services; editorials, opinion pieces, and non-peer-reviewed sources without sufficient scientific rigor (unless used

as contextual or supplementary information); studies published in languages other than English or Bulgarian; and duplicates across databases.

Study selection process

The initial search results were screened based on titles and abstracts to identify potentially relevant publications. Full-text articles were subsequently assessed for eligibility based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Priority was given to high-quality sources, including peer-reviewed articles, official regulatory documents, and reports issued by reputable international and national organizations.

Data extraction and analysis

Data from the selected sources were extracted and analyzed qualitatively. The extracted information included key concepts, definitions, methodological approaches, findings, and conclusions related to telepharmacy and its applications. A thematic analysis approach was applied to identify recurring patterns and group the information into major thematic categories, such as conceptual frameworks, technological infrastructure, regulatory aspects, and practical applications.

Language and contextual considerations

Both English and Bulgarian language publications were included to ensure a comprehensive overview and to incorporate region-specific information relevant to the Bulgarian healthcare context. The inclusion of national data and regulatory documents allowed for a more context-specific analysis of telepharmacy implementation in Bulgaria.

Limitations of the study

This narrative review has several limitations. First, the number of studies specifically addressing the application of telepharmacy in Bulgaria is limited, which may affect the depth of the analysis in the national context. Second, the restriction to English and Bulgarian language sources may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant studies published in other languages. Third, the time frame limited to publications from 2010 onwards may have excluded earlier studies that could provide valuable insights into the historical development of the field. Finally, as a narrative review, the study does not follow a fully systematic protocol, which may introduce a degree of selection bias and limit reproducibility compared to systematic reviews.

Due to the narrative nature of the review, a formal risk-of-bias assessment was not performed; however, priority was given to high-quality peer-reviewed sources. A thematic synthesis approach was applied to organize and interpret the findings.

References were managed using Zotero.

Grey literature sources, including policy documents and reports from international organizations, were also considered. As a narrative review, the study is subject to potential publication bias. No review protocol was registered prior to conducting this narrative review.

Conceptual framework of telepharmacy

Telepharmacy should not be defined as a distinct form of pharmaceutical care *per se*, but rather as a mode of delivering pharmaceutical services. It represents an approach in which established pharmaceutical care activities are provided remotely through the use of digital technologies, telecommunications, and internet-based platforms (Alexander et al. 2017; Marinkovic et al. 2022). In this sense, telepharmacy does not constitute a separate category of care but a technologically mediated method for delivering existing services. It encompasses a wide range of activities, including patient counseling, prescription review, medication therapy monitoring, prevention, and provision of drug-related and health-related information (Marinkovic et al. 2022). Numerous authors have explored the elements that constitute this concept (Sankaranarayanan et al. 2014; Khoshnam-Rad et al. 2022; Dat et al. 2023; RHI-hub n.d.), and Fig. 1 illustrates the main components of the conceptual model.

The model is structured around four primary pillars. First, remote communication between the pharmacist and the patient is a central component. This communication may be conducted via telephone calls, video consultations, mobile applications, or web-based platforms (Kosmisky et al. 2019). Such modalities enable the provision of pharmaceutical counseling, clarification of medication administration, discussion of potential adverse drug reactions, and support for medication adherence. The remote nature of these services is particularly important for patients in rural or hard-to-reach areas.

The second core component includes electronic prescriptions and digital health records. Electronic prescribing facilitates the rapid and secure transmission of information regarding pharmacotherapy between physicians and pharmacists, thereby reducing the risk of errors associated with manual processing or illegible prescriptions (Pesheva et al. 2021, 2022; Toshev et al. 2024). Digital health records provide access to a patient's comprehensive medical history, including previous treatments, allergies, and comorbidities (Ministry of Health 2026). This supports informed decision-making by pharmacists and enhances coordination among healthcare professionals (Clarke et al. 2016).

The third component encompasses systems for therapy monitoring and follow-up, which enable the assessment of treatment effectiveness and safety in real time or over extended periods. These systems allow tracking of parameters such as medication adherence, occurrence of adverse effects, and therapeutic outcomes. In some cases, automated alerts and medication reminders are also implemented.

Figure 1. Main components of telepharmacy.

Such tools enable timely pharmacist intervention when problems are identified and contribute to the optimization of pharmacotherapy (Schiepek et al. 2016; Morillo-Verdugo et al. 2022; Jafleh et al. n.d.).

The fourth component, health promotion, represents an important extension of the pharmacist's public health role within the context of telepharmacy, enabled through the use of digital and telecommunication technologies. By providing remote access to counseling, education, and preventive interventions, telepharmacy facilitates the dissemination of reliable health information to broader and potentially underserved populations (Frenzel and Porter 2023; Ilkić et al. 2023).

In this context, pharmacists can actively support patients in adopting healthier behaviors, improving medication adherence, and managing chronic conditions through continuous digital engagement (Ivanova et al. 2021a; Livet et al. 2021; Dores et al. 2023). Furthermore, telepharmacy enhances the effectiveness of health promotion strategies by enabling timely, personalized, and data-driven interventions, thereby contributing to improved health outcomes and overall population health (Umar et al. 2023).

The interaction among these components creates an integrated environment for the delivery of pharmaceutical services, improving access to care, enhancing treatment safety, and supporting more effective medication management (Kilova et al. 2020, 2021b; Curran et al. 2023).

The following indicators are selected to provide a structured comparison between telepharmacy and conventional pharmacy practice, focusing on key aspects of pharmaceutical service delivery (Umar et al. 2023). They include

core professional activities such as patient consultation, medication therapy management, monitoring, communication, and health promotion (Manuel et al. 2022; Naqi et al. 2022; Curran et al. 2023; Santos et al. 2023). These parameters highlight differences in accessibility, interaction modality, and the integration of digital technologies. Overall, the indicators enable a clearer understanding of how telepharmacy transforms and extends traditional pharmaceutical practice (Blenkinsopp et al. 2003; Delorme et al. 2011; Manuel et al. 2022; Marinkovic et al. 2022; Alarfaj et al. 2024; Sherazi et al. 2024; Snoswell et al. 2025).

Technological framework of telepharmacy

The technological foundation of the telepharmacy model includes reliable internet access, video consultation capabilities, specialized software platforms, and integration with electronic health systems. In several of these areas, Bulgaria still lags behind other European countries, particularly in terms of full digitalization and effective interoperability between different healthcare system components (European Parliament 2011; DESI 2025; Ministry of Health 2025).

Since 2020, the National Health Information System has been operational in Bulgaria, integrating patient data into a structured and processable format (Ministry of Health 2026). Through the establishment of electronic patient records, citizens have access to their personal health information and can monitor medical data, including prescribed therapies, medical examinations, vaccinations, and laboratory diagnostic tests (Ministry of Health 2025, 2026).

Table 1. Comparison of pharmaceutical services in telepharmacy and conventional pharmacy practice.

Pharmaceutical activity/ indicator	Telepharmacy (role of the pharmacist)	Conventional pharmacy (role of the pharmacist)
Pharmaceutical consultation	Conducted remotely via videoconferencing platforms, chat, or telephone; requires advanced digital communication skills	Conducted face-to-face, allowing direct observation and more comprehensive communication
Medication therapy review	Performed through access to electronic health records and shared data systems	Performed through direct contact with the patient and access to available documentation
Therapy monitoring	Based on digital tools, mobile applications, and electronic health platforms	Based on periodic visits and direct personal communication with the patient
Medication safety interventions	Carried out through remote communication and electronic alerts/notifications	Carried out immediately, often allowing for prompt intervention and response
Therapy adherence monitoring	Utilizing digital systems, reminders, and analysis of data from applications	Through patient interviews and observation during visits
Interdisciplinary communication	Facilitated through electronic platforms, shared health systems, and virtual meetings	Direct communication with physicians and other healthcare professionals
Electronic prescription handling (e-prescribing)	A core component—electronic receipt, verification, and processing of prescriptions	Supporting role—processing of both paper-based and electronic prescriptions
Health promotion and prevention	Delivered through digital campaigns, online consultations, and educational platforms	Delivered through in-person consultations, printed materials, and in-pharmacy campaigns
Patient access	Significantly expanded access—including remote and hard-to-reach populations	Limited to patients physically present in the pharmacy
Role of the pharmacist	Digitally oriented, with an emphasis on remote clinical pharmacy services and data management	Clinical and consultative, based on direct contact and observation

The implementation and further development of this system provide the necessary infrastructural basis for the future deployment of remote pharmaceutical services. This would enable improved coordination among healthcare professionals, more effective control of pharmacotherapy, and opportunities for regulation and monitoring in accordance with national legislation (Dores et al. 2023; Santos et al. 2023). Furthermore, integration with broader digital health components would facilitate the delivery of remote pharmaceutical care and improve the overall quality of patient services (Pathak et al. 2020; Obradovic et al. 2025). This is defined as telepharmacy services with a focus on digital platform development.

The development of digital infrastructure, combined with appropriate regulatory mechanisms, has the potential to reduce inequalities in access to healthcare and to ensure timely pharmaceutical consultation and therapy monitoring for populations in underserved areas (Livet et al. 2021; Hatem 2024; Ministry of Health 2025).

Video consultations play a crucial role in the delivery of contemporary pharmaceutical services, as they enable effective remote communication between pharmacists and patients. In many cases, visual demonstration is essential during the consultation process—for example, demonstrating the correct use of dosage forms (such as inhalers or injectable devices), interpreting medication labels, or presenting medical devices. In addition, video consultations support a more individualized approach by allowing better assessment of the patient's condition through visual and behavioral cues (Pathak et al. 2020; Marinkovic et al. 2022; Naqvi et al. 2022).

They are particularly beneficial for patients with limited access to healthcare services, including those with chronic conditions or elderly individuals for whom visiting a

pharmacy or healthcare facility may be challenging (Poude and Nissen 2016a; Cigolle and Phillips 2023). In the context of healthcare digitalization and the advancement of telemedicine, video consultations are increasingly recognized as a key tool for improving both the quality and accessibility of pharmaceutical care (Edrees et al. 2022; De Tran et al. 2023). They contribute to better therapy monitoring, improved medication adherence, and a reduced risk of medication-related errors (Livet et al. 2021).

Depending on patient needs, the application of telepharmacy can be categorized into three main domains, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Community telepharmacy is the most widely adopted domain of telepharmacy. In this setting, pharmacists provide services to ambulatory patients. For individuals with chronic conditions, consultations are typically non-urgent; however, the complexity of therapeutic regimens and the prevalence of polypharmacy necessitate additional time and a structured environment to ensure the provision of accurate, patient-centered pharmaceutical care in accordance with established professional standards (Clifton et al. 2003; Viegas et al. 2022; Cigolle and Phillips 2023; Dat et al. 2023; Ilkić et al. 2023; Bruns et al. 2024).

Hospital telepharmacy is a less commonly discussed domain. It is applied when consultation with hospital pharmacists is required regarding therapies prescribed and dispensed within a healthcare institution (Morillo-Verdugo et al. 2023; Barbadillo-Villanueva et al. 2024). This model is most often relevant for hospitalized patients who require continued long-term treatment for specific conditions, necessitating strict monitoring of therapeutic outcomes and ongoing professional supervision (Antonio Solana-Altabella et al. 2023; Khare 2025; Rosalia Fernández-Caballero et al. n.d.).

Figure 2. Main domains of telepharmacy.

A fundamental distinction between hospital telepharmacy and services provided in community (public) pharmacies lies in the degree of patient autonomy in selecting a pharmaceutical provider. In the hospital setting, patients do not have the ability to choose their hospital pharmacist; instead, pharmaceutical care is assigned internally by the institution, typically based on organizational structure, availability of staff, and clinical specialization (Antonio Solana-Altabella et al. 2023; Morillo-Verdugo et al. 2023; Rosalia Fernández-Caballero et al. n.d.). This raises an important practical and ethical consideration regarding whether such allocation consistently ensures continuity, personalization, and optimal quality of care (Obradovic et al. 2025).

By contrast, within the community pharmacy sector, patients retain full freedom of choice. They may select not only the pharmacy they prefer but also, in many cases, establish ongoing professional relationships with specific pharmacists. This element of choice can enhance patient trust, satisfaction, and adherence to therapy, as it allows for continuity of care based on individual preference. Consequently, the lack of such autonomy in hospital telepharmacy represents a notable structural difference, which may influence patient perception and engagement with pharmaceutical services.

Consultative telepharmacy is a relatively recently described domain within telepharmacy. It has emerged in response to the growing demand for accessible, reliable health-related information among the general population. With the expansion of digital technologies, an increasing number of individuals seek health information online; however, such information is frequently unverified, inaccurate, or potentially harmful. Moreover, patients are often unable to critically appraise the reliability of the information they encounter (Hou and Shim 2010; Clarke et al. 2016; Marinkovic et al. 2022; Hatem 2024; Rodrigues et al. 2024).

Consultative telepharmacy provides an opportunity for individuals to receive professional guidance on a wide

range of health-related topics from qualified pharmacists. This approach has the potential to improve the quality of information available to patients and, indirectly, to support informed decision-making regarding their health and treatment (Hou and Shim 2010; Manuel et al. 2022; Viegas et al. 2022).

Status of pharmaceutical services in Bulgaria

Pharmacists are among the most accessible healthcare professionals. Due to the widespread distribution of pharmacies in larger urban areas, good physical access for patients is ensured, while the provision of free pharmaceutical consultations guarantees the financial accessibility of the service (PGEU n.d.).

However, numerous studies indicate existing disparities in the distribution of pharmaceutical resources (Krumov et al. 2017; Pesheva and Ivanova 2023). A study from 2019 identified an uneven distribution of pharmacists and pharmacies, with a clear concentration in larger cities at the expense of smaller settlements (Krumov and Grigorov 2019). Additional studies confirm this issue and highlight the limited access to pharmacies that handle controlled (narcotic) substances, as well as those that prepare medicinal products from magisterial recipes or pharmacopoeia prescriptions (Pesheva and Ivanova 2023; Pesheva et al. 2024). Data from 2023 show that in some regions and municipalities, there is a lack of 24-hour pharmacies and access to specialized pharmaceutical services.

These factors necessitate alternative approaches to accessing pharmaceutical care. In many cases, patients seek not only the dispensing of medicinal products but primarily professional consultation. Modern technologies and the development of telepharmacy enable part of these consultations to be conducted in a digital environment. Online pharmaceutical services allow patients

to receive the necessary information and guidance in the comfort of their own homes, without the limitations of the physical setting. Furthermore, the high level of confidentiality in remote communication contributes to a more relaxed and open consultation.

According to data from the National Statistical Institute at the beginning of 2024, Bulgaria has over 1.5 million citizens aged over 65, out of a total population of approximately 6.4 million (NSI 2024). This demographic structure further emphasizes the need for more accessible and flexible pharmaceutical services, as elderly patients often face difficulties in accessing pharmacies physically.

In summary, the pharmaceutical system in Bulgaria is well developed in urban areas but is characterized by a significantly uneven distribution of pharmacies and pharmacists (Pesheva and Ivanova 2023). This creates prerequisites for the implementation of innovative solutions such as remote pharmaceutical services, which can improve equitable access to healthcare (Krumov and Grigorov 2019; Pesheva and Ivanova 2023).

The legislative framework in Bulgaria is primarily governed by the Medicinal Products in Human Medicine Act, which defines the conditions for the trade, dispensing, and control of medicinal products (Ministry of Health 2007). Despite advances in digital health, including the introduction of electronic prescriptions, telepharmacy is still not clearly defined as an independent practice within national legislation (Ministry of Health 2007, 2025).

According to the current regulatory framework, the remote dispensing of prescription-only medicinal products is not permitted (Ministry of Health 2007). However, there is no explicit prohibition of providing pharmaceutical consultations remotely, including for previously prescribed and dispensed medicinal products. All other non-prescription products may be sold online through pharmacy websites registered with the Bulgarian Drug Agency (Ministry of Health 2007; Pesheva et al. 2024).

A significant issue in practice is that a considerable proportion of over-the-counter medicinal products may interact with prescribed medications, potentially leading to adverse reactions, drug interactions, and other negative treatment outcomes (Andy et al. 2024). During in-person pharmacy consultations, patients often do not provide complete information about all products they are using, which increases the risk of drug interactions and medication errors (Clifton et al. 2003; Peláez Bejarano et al. 2021; Marinkovic et al. 2022; Snoswell et al. 2025).

In this context, telepharmacy offers a potential solution by creating a more relaxed and trustworthy communication environment. Conducting consultations in a home setting enables patients to present their available medicinal products (e.g., packaging), even when they have difficulty describing them. This facilitates a more accurate assessment by the pharmacist and allows for appropriate guidance. With the increasing proportion of an aging population, these challenges in pharmacy consultations are expected to grow (Steckler 2016).

Moreover, the remote format allows pharmacists to dedicate more time to each patient, which is essential for conducting thorough consultations, verifying patient understanding, and improving medication adherence. In this way, telepharmacy can contribute to enhancing both the quality and safety of pharmaceutical services within the existing regulatory framework (Obradovic et al. 2025).

Implementation of telepharmacy in Bulgaria

The implementation of telepharmacy in Bulgaria remains at an early stage, largely due to the slower development of national e-health systems compared to other European countries (Kilova et al. 2021b). This is driven by structural, regulatory, and technological barriers that limit the integration of digital health systems. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of ICT, positioning telepharmacy as an effective tool for maintaining pharmaceutical care during restricted access to healthcare. It demonstrated both the feasibility and value of remote services in ensuring patient safety, adherence, and continuity of care (Kilova et al. 2021b; Pathak et al. 2021; Khoshnam-Rad et al. 2022).

Professional and public attitudes in Bulgaria

A study of 379 respondents, predominantly healthcare professionals (mean age 44.38 years), indicates high digital engagement, with over 90% using the internet for health information (Kilova et al. 2021b). This reflects adequate digital literacy for telepharmacy adoption (Jarab et al. 2024). Many respondents expressed willingness to engage in remote consultations and medication monitoring via mobile applications, highlighting perceived benefits in convenience and care quality (Cigolle and Phillips 2023). However, over 56% were reluctant to purchase prescription medicines online, mainly due to concerns about safety, authenticity, and the lack of clear regulation (Kilova et al. 2021b).

Service expansion and efficiency

Telepharmacy has significant potential to improve healthcare accessibility and efficiency, particularly in rural or underserved areas lacking pharmacists. It enables remote consultations and better resource allocation. Evidence from international models and pilot initiatives suggests improved workflow efficiency, reduced in-person visits, and optimized use of professional expertise (Kilova et al. 2021a). It also supports value-added services such as medication therapy management and adherence monitoring. However, implementation in community pharmacies remains limited due to infrastructural and organizational challenges (Balkanski et al. 2019).

Challenges and limitations

Telepharmacy in Bulgaria is characterized by high digital engagement alongside skepticism toward specific

applications, particularly online medicine purchases. This reflects both user readiness and systemic limitations, especially regulatory gaps and low institutional trust.

Professional and public readiness

The same study confirms strong digital literacy, with widespread use of online health information (Kilova et al. 2021b). Respondents show willingness to use telepharmacy for consultations and therapy monitoring, indicating growing acceptance. Nevertheless, reluctance toward online purchasing persists (over 56%), driven by concerns about medicine safety, authenticity, and insufficient regulation, further compounded by distrust linked to unregulated product markets (Kilova et al. 2021b).

Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic

The pandemic marked a turning point by necessitating the adoption of remote healthcare delivery. Telepharmacy ensured continuity of care and facilitated pharmacist–patient interaction without physical contact. Despite prior delays in e-health implementation, pharmacists increasingly adopted digital tools, thereby demonstrating the feasibility of telepharmacy and its capacity to enhance healthcare system resilience (Kilova et al. 2021a; Sarasmita et al. n.d.).

System feasibility and resource efficiency

International evidence and pilot studies confirm the feasibility and efficiency of telepharmacy. Systems such as TPRSS demonstrate user acceptance rates exceeding 80% following trial use (Lebl et al. 2017). Common services include prescription ordering and over-the-counter medication purchases, which reduce the burden on healthcare facilities. Furthermore, the integration of ICT enhances workflow efficiency and optimizes resource allocation, particularly in underserved regions (Kilova et al. 2021a, 2021b; Curran et al. 2023).

Key barriers

The main limitation is the lack of a comprehensive legal and strategic framework regulating telepharmacy. This affects licensing, standards of care, data protection, and remote dispensing. Regulatory uncertainty also reduces trust, particularly regarding data security (Kilova et al. 2021b, 2021a). Addressing these issues requires coordinated efforts among public institutions, the private sector, and academia to develop clear policies and standards, facilitating safe implementation and improving healthcare system performance (Steckler 2016; Kilova et al. 2021b).

Discussion

The rapid evolution of information and communication technologies has revolutionized healthcare delivery, necessitating a re-evaluation of traditional models of pharmaceutical

care (Poudel and Nissen 2016b; Kosmisky et al. 2019). In this context, telepharmacy emerges as a transformative solution, enabling pharmacists to deliver clinical services and medication counseling to patients at a distance (Baltoni et al. 2019; Kilova et al. 2021b). In Bulgaria, this paradigm shift is particularly urgent, as the nation currently lags in the comprehensive integration of e-health infrastructure (Kilova et al. 2021a). The implementation of such remote pharmaceutical services offers a viable strategy to mitigate the persistent shortage of pharmacy professionals and improve access to care in underserved regions (Kilova et al. 2021b). Furthermore, the adoption of these digital platforms aligns with the increasing reliance on online health information among the Bulgarian population, which serves as a foundation for broader user acceptance of virtual counseling (Kilova et al. 2021b). The global health crisis has further underscored the necessity of these systems, as physical distancing mandates highlighted the critical role of technology in maintaining continuity of care (Kilova et al. 2021a; Hursman et al. 2024). By bridging the gap between pharmacists and patients in rural areas, telepharmacy can address significant geographical disparities in health accessibility while enhancing clinical safety through standardized medication monitoring (Poudel and Nissen 2016b; Hursman et al. 2024). Moreover, the integration of electronic prescribing and remote patient monitoring tools could significantly streamline medication management and minimize prescription errors within the Bulgarian healthcare framework (Almeman 2024; Alsoweih et al. 2024). Recent evidence from Bulgaria highlights that high workload, staffing shortages, and administrative burden are major determinants of pharmacist burnout, affecting the quality of pharmaceutical care (Ivanova et al. 2023). In line with EU pharmaceutical policy and WHO recommendations emphasizing digital transformation, transparency, and improved access to medicines as key pillars of sustainable healthcare systems, the implementation of electronic prescribing enhances medication safety and regulatory oversight but also introduces additional organizational demands, reinforcing the need for integrated digital and telepharmacy solutions (Ivanova et al. 2026; Todorova et al. 2026). In this context, this transition towards virtual service delivery not only facilitates greater operational efficiency but also enhances interprofessional collaboration and optimizes the allocation of existing health resources (Lizano-Díez et al. 2022). By enabling remote prescription verification and medication reviews, this model empowers pharmacists to provide essential support to chronically ill patients and those with limited mobility, effectively positioning the profession as a robust frontline service (Poudel and Nissen 2016b; Ivanova et al. 2021b; Cigolle and Phillips 2023; De Tran et al. 2023).

Telepharmacy represents an innovative and promising model for the delivery of pharmaceutical services that can significantly improve both access to and the quality of healthcare in Bulgaria. However, its effective implementation requires coordinated policy and system-level reforms. These include revisions to the national regulatory framework to formally recognize and govern telepharmacy practices. The full implementation of electronic health records is also necessary, with

ensured access for pharmacists to relevant patient information. In addition, a secure and interoperable digital platform for telepharmacy services should be developed. Education and training programs for both pharmacists and patients are essential to support the effective use of digital technologies. Finally, appropriate incentive mechanisms should be introduced to encourage both healthcare professionals and patients to adopt and use remote pharmaceutical care services.

Conclusion

Despite the presence of several challenges related to regulation, technological infrastructure, and acceptance by healthcare professionals, the potential benefits are substantial. With an appropriate regulatory framework and adequate investment, telepharmacy could become an important component of the modern healthcare system (Steckler 2016).

Future research will focus on conducting comparative analyses of the opportunities for implementing telepharmacy in Bulgaria in relation to other European Union Member States and countries worldwide to identify best practices and context-specific challenges. Additionally, further investigation is warranted into the role of telepharmacy as a reliable and evidence-based source of health information for patients, potentially serving as a preferable alternative to general internet searches.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Union–NextGeneration EU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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